

Assessment of Knowledge, Attitude and Prevalence of Drug Abuse among Federal Colleges of Education Students in Nigeria

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Abstract

Drug abuse is one of the major health challenges and of a great concern to the government and also the general public. This study sought to determine the knowledge level, attitudes, prevalence, contributing factors and intervention strategies towards drug abuse among Federal Colleges of Education students in Nigeria. The research design used was descriptive cross-sectional among the NCE II Biology students. A multistage sampling technique was adopted; one Federal College of Education each was selected from the six geo political zones. A total of 1572 subjects were the sample. The study has Six research questions and hypotheses respectively. Structured questionnaire named Students' Knowledge Attitude Prevalence of Drug Abuse Questionnaire (SKAPODAQ) was used to collect data online through a kobo tool box. The questionnaire was based on Likert 5-point rating scale. Descriptive statistics of frequencies and percentage were used to analyze the Demo graph of the respondents, Mean and Standard Deviation for research questions (SPSS version-20.0) while Chi-Square statistics and Pearson Correlation was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Result of rho obtained was 0.73. The result revealed that the most of the respondents were young people (16-22) years 86.3%, male having the highest number; That NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria have the knowledge (4.162) and positive attitude (3.385) to the use of drugs and abuse. Majority of the students agreed that the contributing factors such as using drugs to achieve feeling to joy and happiness (33.7%), use drugs during exams (52.7 %) use medication without valid prescription (62.3%) influence the prevalence of drug abuse. The study also agreed that relationship exist among knowledge, attitude, prevalence and contributing factors to drug abuse. Therefore, recommends that more awareness should be created on the negative effects of drug abuse among students in Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria which on the other hand will reduce the prevalence rate.

Keywords: Knowledge, Attitude, Prevalence, Drug Abuse

Introduction

Drug abuse refers to the harmful or hazardous use of psychoactive substances, including both legal and illegal drugs. It involves the use of substances such as alcohol, prescription medications, or illicit drugs in a way that leads to physical, psychological, or social harm to the individual. It is an intrinsic health behavior according to (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, 2021) that can result in addiction health problems, impaired judgment, and negative consequences in various aspects of a person's life (Dibia., Nwagu & Odo 2020). Drug abuse is of significant concern in Developing countries, especially among students of tertiary institutions. According to UNODC (2021) about 275 million people used drugs worldwide while over 36 million people suffered from drug use disorders. Drug abuse, among the most common public health problems for both adults and adolescents, is of significant societal concern Abuhuraira., Yusuf., Muhammad., Mamman., Solomon., Umar & Muhammad, (2021).

Federal Colleges of Education is tertiary institutions that award students with a Nigerian Certificate in Education (NCE) Degree. During this period in school, students experience independence and freedom from adult and parent supervision, form new social groups, make decisions by themselves, and balance some social engagements and life responsibilities with

their academics. They also imbibe some normative values and youth culture that differ from their parental background. Most of the Federal College of Education students are in their Adolescence stage, a vital stage of life and the most transformative time in life Makanjuola., Daramola & Obembe (2007) and Alhyas., Ozaibi., Elarabi., El-Kashef., Wanigaratne & Almarzouqi (2015). These perceived norms motivate the youth to indulge in some unhealthy behaviors, such as smoking, alcohol, and drugs, that could change their perceptions, mood, cognition, and behavior (Alhyas., Ozaibi., Elarabi., El-Kashef., Wanigaratne & Almarzouqi (2015). Researchers like Herold., Boykan., Eliscu., Alcalá., & Gronkiewicz (2021) and Desmennu., Titiloye & Owoaje (2018) grouped the abused drugs as follows: stimulants, such as amphetamines and cocaine, which increase alertness and energy levels. Depressants, such as alcohol and benzodiazepines, slow down the central nervous system and induce relaxation—hallucinogens, such as LSD and psilocybin mushrooms, which alter perception and mood. Barati., Bashirian., Jormand., Babamiri., & Rezapur-Shahkolai (2022) and Umukoro., Eduviere., Ahama., Moke., Edje., Omorodion & Ovigue (2021) said that Opioids, including prescription painkillers and heroin are highly addictive substances that create a sense of euphoria. Cannabis, also known as marijuana, is another commonly abused drug among adolescents (UNODC,2021). Several researchers have linked drug abuse with some unhealthy behaviors like depression, violence, crimes like rape, stealing, prostitution, and sex work, this create nuisance to the society (Racionero-Plaza., León., Iglesias., & Ugalde 2021). Constant uses cause serious problem and irreversible damage on individual's physical and development, a significant societal concern that affects worldwide, including students pursuing higher education Akinsefunmi, Rita, Aminat & Rufus (2016) and Onoyase, (2019). Understanding the knowledge level, attitudes, prevalence, contributing factors to drug abuse is crucial for developing targeted prevention, control and intervention strategies to address the issue effectively. It is in this context that drug abuse becomes an addiction for most adolescents in schools. Drug abuse among adolescents in schools is a complex issue that is influenced by multiple factors with the problem increasing day by day Racionero-Plaza., León., Iglesias., & Ugalde (2021). In recent years, drug abuse has become a growing problem among students in tertiary institutions with potentially detrimental consequences for their academic performance and personal well-being. Federal Colleges of Education is not left out. It was against these backdrops that the researchers sought to investigate the Knowledge Level, Attitude and Prevalence of Drug Abuse among Nigerian Certificate Education Students in Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria. This assessment will provide insights into the existing gaps in their understanding of the risks associated with drug abuse and shed light on their prevalence, perceptions, beliefs and attitudes toward the misuse of drugs, it will offer valuable information for designing targeted interventions and also identifying the contributing factors. Unraveling these factors will help in developing comprehensive prevention strategies that will likely address the root causes of these situation among students in Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria.

Recent studies in Nigeria and worldwide have shown that a significant percentage of drug abusers seeking treatment and rehabilitation are adolescents and students (Jyotika & Pradeep, 2017, Chetty 2018 and Nwagu., Dibia & Odo 2020). An estimation of about 275 million people worldwide are engaged in drug abuse (UNODC,2021). In Nigeria, drug abuse is prevalent among youths, many of whom are unaware of the dangers associated with drug addiction (Ofili., Ugorume., Oyibocho & Eziashi 2021 Sarkingobir & Dikko, 2020 and Uroko, 2022) with potential consequences on their academic performance and overall well-being. However, there is a lack of comprehensive understanding regarding the knowledge level, attitudes, prevalence, contributing factors, and effectiveness of prevention and intervention strategies in addressing this issue (Mayanchi, et. al., 2020). This knowledge gap hinders the development of targeted and evidence-based approaches to combat drug abuse. Therefore, there is a need to investigate the knowledge, attitudes, prevalence, contributing factors and intervention strategies for drug abuse among students in Federal Colleges of Education.

Objectives of the Study

1. Determine the knowledge level and its prevalence on drug abuse among NCE II Biology Students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria
2. What is the attitude and prevalence of drug abuse among NCE II Biology Students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria?
3. Do contributing factors to drug abuse influence the prevalence rate among NCE II Biology Students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria
4. Do Intervention Strategies assessment influence the prevalence of drug abuse among NCE II Biology Students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria.
5. Investigate the relationship among knowledge level, attitude, prevalence and contributing factors to drug abuse among NCE II Biology Students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria

Assessment of Knowledge, Attitude ... (Ezeaghasi, et. al., 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10654693>

Research Questions

1. Does knowledge level of NCE II Biology Students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria have no significant influence on prevalence of drug abuse?
2. Does the attitude of NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria towards drug abuse have no significant influence on prevalence?
3. Do contributing factors to drug abuse influence the prevalence among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria?
4. Do Intervention Strategies assessment influence the prevalence of drug abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria?
5. What is the relationship between the knowledge level, attitude, prevalence and contributing factors to drug abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria?

Hypotheses

1. Knowledge level of NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education have no significant influence on prevalence of drug abuse
2. Attitude of NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education towards drug abuse have no significant influence on prevalence.
3. Contributing factors to drug abuse have no significant influence on the prevalence among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education
4. Intervention Strategies Assessment have no significance influence on the prevalence of among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education
5. There is no significant relationship among knowledge level, attitude, prevalence and contributing factors to drug abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education.

Methodology

The research design was a descriptive survey which was carried out for a period of six months (July to Dec 2023). All NCE II Biology students of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria with a total of 4912 students that registered in 2022/2023 Academic Session were the population. A multistage sampling technique was adopted; one Federal College of Education each was selected from the six geo political zones. One thousand five hundred and seventy-two 1572 (943 Male and 629 Female) students were sampled using a simple random sampling technique. Table 1 presented the Sample Study.

Table 1: Sample of the Study

S/N	Colleges of Education	Male	Female	Total
1	Adeyemi College of Education	67	45	112
2	FCE EHA-Amufu	65	43	108
3	FCE Obudu	88	58	146
4	FCE Okene	77	51	128
5	FCE Yola	159	107	266
6	FCE Zaria	487	325	812
Total		943	629	1572

Source: Field Survey (2023)

The research Instrument for the study is Students Knowledge, Attitude and Prevalence of Drug Abuse Questionnaire (SKAPODAQ) which was adapted and developed. The questionnaire comprised of six sections; (1) Demographic Information (2) knowledge Assessment (3) Attitude Assessment (4) Prevalence of Drug abuse (5) Contributing Factors Assessment and (6) Intervention Effectiveness assessment. The questionnaire contained 60 items to reflect on the overall towards Knowledge, Attitude Prevalence, Contributing Factors, Intervention Effectiveness of Drug Abuse among NCE II Biology Students of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. The questionnaire was based on Likert 5-point rating scale.

The rating of the 5-point Likert scale of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A) Undecided (UD) Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD) Scored 5,4321 for positive statement and reverse order for negative statements. The data was collected online using Students Knowledge level, Attitude Prevalence of Drug Abuse Questionnaire (SKAPODAQ) through a kobo tool

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box. Data was analyzed with statistical software (SPSS version-20.0). Descriptive statistics of frequencies and percentage were used for Demography of the respondents. Mean and Standard Deviation was used to answer the research questions while Chi-Square statistics and Pearson Correlation was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results were presented in form of tables. The data was analyzed at the data processing unit of Iya Abubakar Computer Centre, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. The Instrument, Students Knowledge Attitude Prevalence of Drug Abuse Questionnaire (SKAPODAQ) was validated by three experts with qualification of PhD and minimum rank of Senior lecturers in the Department of Psychology, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. Pilot study was carried out to a group of two hundred and fifty (250) students in the Department of Biology, Federal College of Education Katsina, Katsina State for reliability. This college was part of the population but not sampled. The Method of analysis used was Spearman Rank Order Correlation. Result of rho obtained was 0.73 which made the instrument reliable for the study. The researchers administered the questionnaire for five weeks with the help of research assistance in the department.

Table 2: Demographic Data of the Respondents

	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	Standard Deviation
Gender			1.40	0.490
Male	943	60		
Female	629	40		
Age			1.16	0.446
16-22	1356	86.3		
23-26	155	9.9		
27+	49	3.1		
Socio Economic Status			1.33	0.535
Low	1096	69.7		
Middle	426	27.1		
High	50	3.2		
Total	1572	100	1.29	0.49

Source: Field Survey, 2023

This study had 1572 respondents, 943 (60%) were males, 629 (40%) were females, 1356 (86.3%) were within the ages of 16-22 years, 155 (9.9%) were within the ages of 23-26 years, 49(3.1%) were within the ages of 27 and above. The socio – economic status, 1096 (69.7%) were Low, 426(27.1%) middle, 50 (3.2%) high. The result revealed that the majority of the respondents were young people (16-22) years 86.3%, male having the highest number.

Research Question 1

Does Knowledge level of NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria have significant influence on prevalence of drug abuse?

Table 3: Summary of Mean and standard deviation on the knowledge level of NCE II biology students in Nigerian Colleges of Education.

S/N	Variables	SA		A		UN		D		SD		Mean	STD
		F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%		
1	Drug abuse refers to use of illegal substances only	846	53.8	449	28.6	22	1.4	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.16	1.168
2	Mixing alcohol with certain medications can be dangerous and potentially life-threatening	801	51.0	469	29.8	22	1.4	221	14.1	59	3.8	4.10	1.189

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3	Drug addiction is a chronic disease that requires long-term treatment and support	803	51.1	482	30.7	31	2.0	31	2.0	197	12.5	4.13	1.164
4	Using Prescription drugs without a doctor's supervision is safe and poses no risks	831	52.9	464	29.5	22	1.4	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.15	1.165
5	Seeking professional help, such as counselling or rehabilitation, is an effective way to overcome drug addiction	844	53.7	453	28.8	20	1.3	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.16	1.166
6	Impaired judgement and decision making is a potential consequence of drug abuse	843	53.6	453	28.8	21	1.3	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.16	1.167
7	Physical dependence is a potential consequence of drug abuse	846	53.8	450	28.6	22	1.4	195	12.4	59	3.8	4.16	1.166
8	Improved academic performance is a potential consequence of drug abuse	846	53.8	455	28.9	21	1.3	191	12.2	59	3.8	4.17	1.161
9	Mental Health problem is a potential consequence of drug abuse	846	53.8	451	28.7	20	1.3	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.16	1.167
10	Sudden weight loss or gain is a sign or symptom of drug abuse	846	53.8	457	29.1	21	1.3	189	12.0	59	3.8	4.17	1.158
11	Increased social withdrawal is a sign or symptom of drug abuse	846	53.8	459	29.2	20	1.3	188	12.0	59	3.8	4.17	1.157
12	Difficulty concentrating is a sign or symptom of drug abuse	840	53.4	472	30	21	1.3	180	11.5	59	3.8	4.18	1.145
13	Healthy copying skills is an example of a risk factor for drug abuse	846	53.8	469	29.8	20	1.3	178	11.3	59	3.8	4.19	1.144
14	Stable family relationship is an example of a risk factor for drug abuse	839	53.4	488	31.0	20	1.3	166	10.6	59	3.8	4.20	1.126
15	What is the recommended course of action if you suspect a fellow student is struggling	846	53.8	463	29.5	22	1.4	182	11.6	59	3.8	4.18	1.150
Aggregated Mean											4.162	1.159	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

From the aggregated mean (4.162) and a standard deviation of 1.159, the decision mean is 2.50. The aggregated mean (4.162) of knowledge level of students is significantly above 2.50 which is the decision mean. The result means that majority of the respondents agreed that knowledge level of NCE II Biology students have significant influence on prevalence of drug abuse. This indicates that the students have a positive knowledge on drug abuse.

Research Question 2

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Does the attitude of NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria towards drug abuse have significant influence on prevalence? To answer the research question frequency count, percentage of the students' response of aggregated Mean and Standard deviation were calculated and summary presented in table 4.

Table 4: Summary of Mean and standard deviation on the attitude level of NCE II biology students in Federal Colleges of Education.

S/N	Variables	SA		A		UN		D		SD		Mean	STD..
		F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%		
1	I am concerned about the rate of drug abuse among NCE Students	15	1.0	167	10.6	1076	68.4	205	13.0	109	6.9	2.86	0.729
2	Drug abuse is a significant problem that needs to be addressed among NCE students	756	48.1	171	10.9	526	33.5	83	5.3	36	2.3	3.97	1.110
3	I am likely to engage in drug abuse in the future	93	5.9	14	0.9	2	0.1	21	1.3	1442	91.7	1.28	0.984
4	I find drug abuse behavior acceptable among my peers	2	0.1	152	9.7	361	23.0	919	58.5	138	8.8	2.34	0.775
5	I believe drug abuse prevention and intervention programs are effective in raising awareness and promoting a drug-free environment among NCE students	772	49.1	588	37.4	48	3.1	128	8.1	36	2.3	4.23	1.001
6	I am comfortable discussing drug abuse-related topics with my peers	387	24.6	748	47.6	191	12.2	187	11.9	59	3.8	3.77	1.063
7	It is important for NCE students to seek help or support if they are struggling with drugs abuse	613	39.0	661	42.0	109	6.9	140	8.9	49	3.1	4.05	1.046
8	Media and popular culture influence promoting drug abuse among NCE students	758	48.2	680	43.3	90	5.7	19	1.2	25	1.6	4.35	0.779
9	I am likely to intervene if I witness a fellow NCE student engaging in drug abuse	836	53.2	311	19.8	277	17.6	48	3.1	100	6.4	4.10	1.180
10	I am aware of the resources and support available on campus for NCE students struggling with drug abuse	846	53.8	417	26.5	155	9.9	110	7.0	44	2.8	4.22	1.060
11	I am happy with drug abuse because it symbolizes manhood	28	1.8	33	2.1	2	0.1	21	1.3	1488	94.7	1.15	0.686
12	I do not like drug abuse because it interferes with sports and social activities	965	61.4	369	23.5	14	0.9	188	12.0	36	2.3	4.30	1.104

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Aggregated Mean	3.385	0.959
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Source: Field Survey, 2023.

The aggregated mean (3.385) and standard deviation of 0.959, It shows that majority of the students agreed that attitude of NCE II Biology students towards drug abuse have significant influence on prevalence of drug abuse. The table showed that majority of the students strongly agreed that effective raising awareness on Drug abuse will have significant effect on addressing the problem.

Research Question 3:

Do contributing factors Influence the prevalence of drug abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria? To answer this research, question the frequency count, percentage of the students' response of aggregated Mean and Standard deviation were calculated and summary presented in table 5.

Table 5: Summary of Mean and standard deviation on Contributing Factors to Drug Abuse

S/N	Variables	SA		A		UN		D		SD		Mean	STD. Dev.
		F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%		
1	I have used illicit drugs (e.g Marijuana, cocaine, heroin) in my lifetime	157	10.0	211	13.4	73	4.6	340	21.6	791	50.3	2.11	1.405
2	I frequently use illicit drugs in the past year	221	14.1	175	11.1	192	12.2	925	58.8	559	3.8	2.73	1.157
3	I use medications without valid prescription	157	10.0	1111	70.7	201	12.8	94	6.0	9	0.6	3.84	0.701
4	I frequently make use of medications without valid prescription by doctors	980	62.3	419	26.7	8	0.5	128	8.1	37	2.4	4.38	1.009
5	I use drugs to improve my memory during examination	608	38.7	445	28.3	264	16.8	196	12.5	59	3.8	3.42	1.027
6	I have engaged in binge drinking (consuming a large amount of alcohol in a short period)	201	12.8	256	16.3	8	0.5	1071	68.1	36	2.3	2.69	1.163
7	I have used tobacco products (e.g cigarettes, e-cigarettes, smokeless tobacco) in the past year	264	16.8	275	17.5	21	1.3	196	12.5	816	51.9	2.35	1.620
8	I often use drugs during examination	828	52.7	275	17.5	256	16.3	177	11.3	36	2.5	3.34	0.956
9	I make use of injections to take drugs	264	16.8	275	17.5	8	0.5	980	62.3	45	2.9	2.83	1.248
10	I use drugs to achieve feelings of joy and happiness	529	33.7	449	28.6	339	21.6	196	12.5	59	3.8	3.52	1.075
Aggregated Mean											3.077	1.142	

Source; Field Survey, 2023

From the responses, the aggregated mean (3.077) and standard deviation (1.142). The students strongly agreed that contributing factors to Drug Abuse Influence the Prevalence among NCE II Biology Students of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. From the table majority of the students strongly agreed that they use drugs without valid prescription from doctors, during examinations to improve memory and also to achieve feelings of joy and happiness (Muhammad, 2021).

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Research Question 4:

Do intervention strategies assessment influence the prevalence of drug abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria? To answer the research question frequency count, percentage of the students' response of aggregated Mean and Standard deviation were calculated and summary presented in table 6.

Table 6: Summary of Mean and standard deviation on Intervention Strategies Assessment to Drug Abuse

S/N	Variables	SA		A		UN		D		SD		Mean	STD. Dev.
		F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%		
1	Peer Pressure is influential in encouraging drug abuse among NCE students	780	49.6	515	32.8	22	1.4	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.12	1.155
2	I believe that stress and academic pressure contribute to drug abuse among NCE students to a great extent	718	45.7	577	36.7	22	1.4	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.08	1.141
3	Family background is contributory to NCE students engaging in drug abuse	741	47.1	554	35.2	22	1.4	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.10	1.146
4	Poverty is a contributing factor to drug abuse among NCE students	846	53.8	449	28.6	22	1.4	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.16	1.168
5	Lack of awareness about the risks of drug abuse plays a significant role in the prevalence of drug abuse among NCE students	846	53.8	449	28.6	22	1.4	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.16	1.168
6	Media and popular culture promotes drug abuse among NCE students	846	53.8	449	28.6	22	1.4	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.16	1.168
7	Early aggressive behaviors contributes to drug abuse among NCE Students	846	53.8	449	28.6	22	1.4	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.16	1.168
8	Lack of parental supervision adds to drug abuse among NCE students	846	53.8	449	28.6	22	1.4	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.16	1.168
9	Educational campaigns and prevention programs helps in reducing drug abuse among NCE students	846	53.8	449	28.6	22	1.4	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.16	1.168
10	Mental health disorders contributes to drug abuse among NCE students	846	53.8	449	28.6	22	1.4	196	12.5	59	3.8	4.16	1.168
Aggregated Mean											4.142	1.162	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

The aggregated mean (4.142) and standard deviation (1.162). The students strongly agreed that Intervention Strategies Assessment Influence the Prevalence of Drug Abuse among NCE II Biology students of Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. They agreed that Poverty, Lack of parental supervision, Early aggressive behaviors and Lack of awareness about the risks of drug abuse plays a significant role in the prevalence of drug abuse (Umukoro., Eduviere., Ahama., Moke., Edje., Omorodion & Ovigie 2021)

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Research Question 5:

What is the relationship between knowledge level, attitude, prevalence and contributing factors to drug abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria? To answer the research question, frequency count, percentage of the students' response of aggregated Mean and Standard deviation were calculated and summary presented in table 7.

Table 7: Summary of Mean and standard deviation on the relationship between knowledge level, attitude, prevalence and contributing factors to drug abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education.

S/N	Variables	SA		A		UN		D		SD		Mean	STD. Dev.
		F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%	F.	%		
1	I am aware of drug abuse prevention and intervention programs provided by the college	844	53.7	466	29.6	22	1.4	196	12.5	44	2.8	4.19	1.125
2	The prevention and intervention programs are aware of its effectiveness	829	52.7	497	31.6	22	1.4	165	10.5	59	3.8	4.19	1.124
3	I have personally participated in drug abuse prevention or intervention programs offered by the college	846	53.8	471	30.0	22	1.4	174	11.1	59	3.8	4.19	1.139
4	Psychosocial interventions can effectively help with drug disorders	846	53.8	463	29.5	22	1.4	182	11.6	59	3.8	4.18	1.150
5	Short-term interventions can reduce alcohol use or related problems for adolescents and young adults	824	52.4	487	31.0	22	1.4	180	11.5	59	3.8	4.17	1.143
6	Juvenile drug courts do not have an effect on drug and alcohol offense recidivism of future drug use	844	53.7	464	29.5	22	1.4	183	11.6	59	3.8	4.18	1.151
7	Drug abuse prevention and intervention resources on the college campus is very accessible	816	51.9	493	31.4	20	1.3	184	11.7	59	3.8	4.16	1.146
Aggregated Mean											4.180	1.139	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

From the responses, the aggregated mean (4.180) and standard deviation (1.139) strongly agreed that there is relationship among knowledge level, attitude, prevalence and contributing factors to drug abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria. Majority of the students are aware of prevention and intervention programs provided by the colleges and that Psychosocial interventions can effectively help with drug disorders.

Hypothesis 1:

Knowledge Level of NCE II Biology Students in Federal Colleges of Education have no Significant Influence on Prevalence of Drug Abuse. Chi-square test was used to analyze the data collected and summary presented in table 8.

Table 8: Summary of chi-square test on the Knowledge Level of NCE II Biology Students in Federal Colleges of Education.

Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)

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Pearson Chi-Square	6111.265 ^a	340	.000
Likelihood Ratio	3037.121	340	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	336.010	1	<.000
N of Valid Cases	1572		

a. 333 cells (88.1%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .00.

From the table above, the knowledge of NCE students in Federal College of Education have significant influence on the prevalence of drug abuse at ($p < 0.05$). The p-value of $< .000$ is less than the 0.05 level of significance, suggesting that there is a statistically significant difference. Based on the result, the null hypothesis which stated that Knowledge level of NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigerian have no significant influence on Prevalence of Drug Abuse is therefore rejected implying that knowledge level influence prevalence of drug abuse among the students.

Hypothesis 2:

Attitude of NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria towards drug abuse have no significant influence on prevalence. Chi-square test was used to analyze the data collected and summary presented in table 9.

Table 9: Summary of chi-square test on the attitude level of NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria towards drug abuse and prevalence.

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	9958.003 ^a	560	.000
Likelihood Ratio	4627.362	560	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	285.448	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	1572		

a. 535 cells (87.8%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .00.

From the table above, the attitude of NCE students in Nigerian College of Education have significant influence on the prevalence of drug abuse ($p < 0.05$). The hypothesis was carried out in order to test whether attitude of NCE students towards drug abuse influence prevalence of drug abuse. Based on the result, the null hypothesis which stated that Attitude of NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education towards drug abuse have no significant influence on prevalence of drug abuse is therefore rejected implying that attitude towards drug abuse influence prevalence of drug abuse among the students.

Hypothesis 3:

Contributing factors to drug abuse have no significant influence on the prevalence among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education. Chi-square test was used to analyze the data collected and summary presented in table 10.

Table 10 Summary of chi-square test on the Contributing factors to drug abuse and prevalence among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education?

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5447.220 ^a	120	.000
Likelihood Ratio	3254.319	120	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	352.474	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	1572		

a. 98 cells (66.7%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .01.

From the table above, the Contributing factors to drug abuse have significant influence on the prevalence of drug abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education ($p < 0.05$). The hypothesis was carried out in order to find out if the identified contributing factors to Drug Abuse Influence Prevalence of Drug Abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education in Nigeria. Based on the result, the null hypothesis which stated that Contributing

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factors to drug abuse have no significant influence on the prevalence of drug abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education. The significance value is 0.00 (i.e., $p = 0.00$), below 0.05. This is because the p -value of 0.00 is substantially lower than the threshold value of 0.05. then the null hypothesis is rejected implying that identified contributing factors to drug abuse influence prevalence of drug abuse.

Hypothesis 4:

Intervention strategies assessment have no significant influence on the prevalence of drug abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education. Chi-square test was used to analyze the data collected and summary presented in table 11.

Table 11: Summary of Chi-square test on Intervention Strategies Assessment on the prevalence of drug abuse among NCEII Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria.?

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	6262.129 ^a	280	.000
Likelihood Ratio	3003.468	280	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	335.727	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	1572		

a. 275 cells (87.3%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .00.

From the result obtained, Intervention Strategies Assessment have significant influence on the prevalence of drug abuse among the students at ($p < 0.05$). The hypothesis was carried out in order to find out whether Intervention Strategies Assessment Influence Prevalence of Drug Abuse. The significance value is 0.00 (i.e., $p = 0.00$), below 0.05. This is because the p -value of 0.00 is substantially lower than the threshold value of 0.05. Based on the result, the null is therefore rejected implying that Intervention Strategies Assessment Significantly Influence Prevalence of Drug Abuse among the students.

Hypothesis 5:

There is no significant relationship among Knowledge Level, Attitude, Prevalence and Contributing Factors to Drug Abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria. Pearson Moment Correlation test was used to analyze the data collected and summary presented in table 12.

Table 12: Summary of Pearson Moment Correlation test on the relationship between Knowledge Level, Attitude, Prevalence and Contributing Factors to Drug Abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria.

		Knowledge	Attitude	Prevalence	Contributing
Knowledge	Pearson Correlation	1	.962**	.462**	.997**
	Sig. (2-Tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	1572	1572	1572	1572
Attitude	Pearson Correlation	.962**	1	.426**	.960**
	Sig. (2-Tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	1572	1572	1572	1572
Prevalence	Pearson Correlation	.462**	.426**	1	.474**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	1572	1572	1572	1572

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Contributing factor	Pearson Correlation	.997**	.960**	.474**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	1572	1572	1572	1572

There is a strong positive relationship among knowledge level, attitude, prevalence and contributing factors to drug abuse among NCE II Biology students and is significant at ($p < 0.05$). The hypothesis was carried out in order to find out whether relationship exists among knowledge level, attitude, prevalence of drug abuse and contributing factors to drug abuse among students. The Pearson Correlation was used to analyze the data as presented in Table 11 at $p \leq 0.05$. The significance value is 0.00 (i.e., $p = 0.00$), below 0.05. This is because the p-value of 0.00 is lower than the threshold value of 0.05.

Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship among knowledge level, attitude, prevalence and contributing factors to drug abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education is rejected.

Discussion of Findings

This study had 1572 respondents, 943 (60%) were males, 629 (40%) were females, 1356 (86.3%) were within the ages of 16-22 years, 155 (9.9%) were within the ages of 23-26 years, 49(3.1%) were within the ages of 27 and above. The majority of the respondent falls within the age range of 16-22 years and male student having the higher proportion. The study is in line with the works of Adeyemo, Okpala & Ohaeri (2016), Ofili, Ugorume, Oyibocha, Eziashi (2021) and Abuhuraira., Yusuf., Muhammad., Mamman., Solomon., Umar & Muhammad, (2021), who agreed that drug abusers are within the above range and majority are male.

The findings of this study revealed that NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria were knowledgeable and had positive attitude to the use drugs and abuse. The result revealed knowledge level (4.162) and attitude (3.385) have significant influence at $p \leq 0.05$ on the prevalence, this findings tallies with the study of Adibe ,Anene- Okeke, Igboeli & Chibueze (2022) on knowledge ,attitude and prevalence of drug abuse among the students. Majority of the students agreed that the contributing factors such as using drugs to achieve feeling to joy and happiness (33.7%) often use drugs during exams (52.7 %) frequently use medication without valid prescription (62.3%) influence the prevalence of drug abuse, this correlates with studies conducted by Adeyemo, Okpala & Ohaeri (2016) that Most students abuse drugs as a result of poor teacher/parental upbringing and also the influence of peer pressure. the null hypothesis which stated that Contributing factors to drug abuse have no significant influence on the prevalence of drug abuse was rejected at $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance implying that identified contributing factors to drug abuse influence prevalence rate. The study also said that Intervention Strategies Assessment Influence the Prevalence of Drug Abuse. The result of the finding concurs with that of Akinsefunmi, Rita, Aminat & Rufus (2016) that Intervention Strategies Assessment Influence the Prevalence of Drug Abuse. Finally, the study strongly agreed that there is relationship among knowledge level, attitude, prevalence and contributing factors to drug abuse.

Conclusion

The study showed that the students in Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria had adequate knowledge and positive attitude towards drug abuse which influence the prevalence among NCE II Biology students. Contributing factors (feelings of joy and improve memory during examination) influence prevalence of drug abuse. Intervention strategies assessment (lack of awareness, peer pressure influence and lack of parental supervision) significantly influence prevalence of drug abuse. Finally, there is Significant relationship among knowledge level, attitude, prevalence, contributing factors and Intervention strategies assessment to drug abuse among NCE II Biology students in Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this work, we recommend that more awareness should be created on the effects of drug abuse among students of Federal Colleges of Education, Nigeria which on the other hand will reduce the prevalence rate. The study also recommends that drug abuse information that addresses social norms and education should be included in the college of education curriculum as a general study for the students as these may have protective outcome.

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